

the system as a result of the actions of harmonious and inter-regulatory institutions.

The integrity of pilgrimage tourism in our country strengthens the existence of the system and its effective operation. In our opinion, the elements of pilgrimage tourism as an existing system are the result of theoretical and methodological approaches specific to systemic theory and systematic analysis.

According to the International Labour Organization, 284 million of the world's working-age population are currently employed in the international tourism system. is busy. Also, one new job created in this industry will be 20 times cheaper than in the industrial sector. For every 30 tourists visiting a country, one or two new jobs are created directly or indirectly.

As a result, it can be concluded that the tourism sector, compared to other sectors of the world economy, serves to create more jobs and provide foreign exchange earnings at a relatively low cost.

The concept of tourism industry has been studied in detail in the scientific literature on tourism in our country. "It consists of a set of organizations for tourism, sports, religious ceremonies, business and other purposes, operating tour operators and tourism agencies, as well as tourism infrastructure organizations".

Canadian experts also acknowledge that the Canadian tourism industry consists of a total of 41 types of services, while U.S. experts say it is necessary to include 39 types of services in the country's tourism industry.

Russian scientists M.E. Nemolyayeva and L.F. Khodorkov have argued that "the modern tourism industry is a group of manufacturers aimed at meeting the needs of people in the countries they visit during their temporary migration for any purpose other than paid professional activities".

In this regard, we believe that the definition of the "tourism industry" is difficult to cover in its entirety. In view of this, we can conclude from the analysis of the above definitions of the concept of "tourism" by scholars and experts through a two-pronged approach to revealing its essence:

1. First, in terms of "demand" for the concept of interpretation of this concept;
2. Secondly, the approach can be observed in terms of "supply".

It should be noted that some views on tourism at the international level also reflect the desire to combine the two approaches. In particular, the Vice-President of the International Academy of Tourism MB Birjakov said: and second, the tourist activity of organizing and conducting these trips. Tourism activities are carried out by the tourism industry and related industries".

Pilgrimage tourism is a complex and open economic system with the following structural classifications:

- market mechanism;
- system of socio-economic relations;
- Organizational and legal forms of management;

- System of incentives and motivation of market participants
- the integrity of elements such as the infrastructure of the tourism market.

Therefore, the mechanism of development of pilgrimage tourism ensures the integrity of these market elements.

As with any economic system, the relationship between pilgrimage tourism and its facilities is regulated by the regulatory mechanisms of a market economy. The mechanism of development of pilgrimage tourism is determined by the economic, social and organizational structure and institutional methods, which perform the function of creating and regulating socio-economic relations with the consumer of consumer goods and sellers of tourist products through systemic interdependence and interdependence. is a combination of zigzag elements and tools.

Only through the development of the components, methods and tools of the mechanism of effective development of pilgrimage tourism in the tourism industry of Uzbekistan will it be possible to achieve the expected results and results in today's global economic development. As a result, we consider it expedient to improve the mechanism of development of pilgrimage tourism on the basis of a structure based on such innovative approaches.

The study of methodological, methodological and practical aspects of this issue is important today in terms of revealing the features and trends in the development of pilgrimage tourism in Uzbekistan and improving the organizational and economic mechanism for its effective development.

Today, in the context of global changes in the world economy and the intensification of the competitive environment, we believe that the organizational and economic mechanism for the effective development of pilgrimage tourism, which is part of our national economy, should be developed through the following elements and methods. In particular, the gradual development of the industry is required with the creation of the necessary laws, decisions and other normative legal acts and the improvement of socio-economic conditions through organizational and institutional mechanisms.

The implementation of such important strategic tasks in the tourism industry of Uzbekistan requires the use of various organizational methods and methodologies in the management of the inter sectoral complex of pilgrimage tourism with the participation of relevant government agencies.

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